

OpenWebSearch.EU

“Piloting a Cooperative Open Web Search Infrastructure to Support Europe’s Digital Sovereignty”

Deliverable D4.2 Report of privacy, transparency, and trust models for search applications V1

Version 1.0

Open Web Search

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Preliminaries

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ii. Project Partners

Acronym	Partner
UNI PASSAU	University of Passau
BADW-LRZ	Leibniz Supercomputing Centre of the Bavarian Academy of Sciences and Humanities
RU	Radboud University
WEBIS	Leipzig University
TUGraz	Graz University of Technology
DLR	German Aerospace Center
IT4I@VSB	Technical University of Ostrava
CERN	Organisation européenne pour la recherche nucléaire
OSF	Open Search Foundation e.V.
A1	A1 Slovenia
CSC	Tieteen tietotekniikan keskus Oy (IT Center for Science)
NLNET	Stichting NLnet
BUW	Bauhaus-Universität Weimar (Associated Partner)
SUMA-EV	SuMa e.V. - Verein für freien Wissenszugang (Associated Partner)

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iv. Deliverable Summary

This document describes the deliverable D4.2 “Report of privacy, transparency, and trust models for search applications” of the OpenWebSearch.eu project funded by the EC under the GA 101070014 within the Horizon Europe Framework programme. It specifies the planning and first activities conducted in the context of search applications and related conceptual models.

¹ Granitzer, M., Voigt, S., Fathima, N. A., Golasowski, M., Guetl, C., Hecking, T., ... & Zerhoudi, S. (2023). Impact and development of an Open Web Index for open web search. Journal of the Association for Information Science and Technology. <https://asistdl.onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1002/asi.24818>

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vii. Executive Summary

This deliverable reports on the initial work on search applications as part of work package 4. According to the work package description, this deliverable is dedicated to the privacy, transparency, and trust models (Task 4.4 and 4.5). A trust and transparency model is outlined in Section 3 that outlines how to foster trust of the user in search engines, but also raises research questions on the relation between trust and transparency. Based on these initial findings empirical user studies are planned that investigate what leads to increased trust based on transparency. A privacy model is described in Section 4 that describes how to maintain user data without violating data protection needs (Section 4). This model is created along the design of the location-based search application and will be further elaborated as part of the development of this application.

Beside the work on these models, initial design work is described in Section 5 that has been performed along the search applications (Task 4.1 and 4.2). It turned out that there is a need to start with the specification of search applications earlier than originally planned (official start date is M13), in order to clarify the integration between index and search application and also to provide input for the requirements to the OWS core, and to assess if the core features and functions support needs for the creation of search applications. In addition to that a prototype of search applications has been developed (Section 5.1) that serves as basis for the search application development in the context of OpenWebSearch.eu, in particular the search applications as part of this work package as the applications to be developed by 3rd party developments.

Hence, the work described in this deliverable provides the basis for the search application development of both the planned demonstration applications within this work package (T4.1 and T4.2), as well as the search applications to be created by external parties.

1. Introduction

One of the key goals of the OpenWebSearch.eu (OWS) project is the creation of an open web index (OWI) that enables the development of various types of applications using web data. Work package 4 aims to support the development of vertical search engines (search applications) based on the OWI in various ways. In contrast to general purpose and large-scale search engines, such as Google or Bing, vertical search engines serve specific domains or purposes, which also provides opportunities to optimize search and retrieval strategies.

The reason for providing support methods is grounded in another key goal of OWS, which is the building of an ecosystem of vertical search engines and other applications based on OWS. Initial steps in this directions consist in the 3rd party call for search applications, as well as the conduction of hackathons where the development of search applications can be tried out.

The support of the development of vertical search applications is provided on different levels. First, technical support is provided by explaining how a search application can be created using the OWS technical infrastructure. This is done by providing a technical documentation and a prototype application, which serves as a blueprint for other applications (see Section 5.1). Second, two search applications are being developed in WP4 (Sections 5.2 and 5.3), in order to demonstrate the feasibility and usefulness of the search application concept and the OWS technical infrastructure. Third, two models are created that support the user experience and user expectations. A trust and transparency model outlines how to foster trust of the user (Section 3). The further elaboration of this model will include empirical user studies that investigate what leads to increased trust based on transparency. A privacy model describes how to maintain user data without violating data protection needs (Section 4). This model is created along the development of the location-based search application.

According to the work package description, this deliverable is dedicated to the privacy, transparency, and trust models. Initial considerations of these models are presented in Section 3 and 4. However, it turned out that there is a need to start with the specification of search applications earlier than originally planned (official start date is M13), in order to clarify the integration between index and search application. Hence, the work described in this deliverable provides the basis for the search application development of both, the planned demonstration applications within this work package, and the search applications created by external parties.

2. Search Paradigms

This section investigates different search paradigms, in order to outline relevant aspects of search engines related to OWS. These paradigms are not mutually exclusive, but are partially overlapping. They also highlight new ways of retrieving information through open web search, increasing trust, and protecting privacy in contrast to features of classical search engines.

2.1 General Search

General search refers to the global search over an entire index that captures a large portion of the web (such as Google web search). Key challenges of general search is the vast size of the index and the ranking. The creation and storage of an index that contains most of the web needs enormous resources. The ranking of documents requires efficient algorithms and significant hardware resources to deliver relevant resources on top of the search result.

OWS will provide an open web index that can be used by front-ends and search applications to enable search for end-users. On the one hand, it is unlikely that OWS can compete with companies such as Google or Bing, regarding ranking and relevance of search results. On the other hand, OWS provides an open index that can be accessed directly and enables applications to perform own selection and ranking. In contrast to Google, that provides restrictions on changing the search result for external applications, OWS offers content-extracted and quality metadata and encourages the adaptation of search results to meet users' requirements.

2.2 Vertical Search Engines

In contrast to general purpose and large-scale search engines, such as Google or Bing, OWS shares the web index for vertical search engines serving specific domains or purposes, which also provides opportunities to optimize search and retrieval strategies. This results in particular benefits for the end user by offering higher precision of the search result, utilisation of domain knowledge in terms of ontologies or knowledge graphs, and facilitating specific user tasks. Today's popular and powerful vertical search solutions mostly pursue commercial purposes or are part of enterprises' business models, such as product search of Amazon, people search of LinkedIn, or hotel search of Booking.com. Even Google maintains vertical search engines (e.g. YouTube) and is interested in further vertical search solution as recently demonstrated through the purchase of the ITA Travel Search Company. Presently, vertical search engines become a more and more active field for commercial purposes, such as marketing, product vending, awareness capturing.

In order to enable the development of search verticals, OWS enables to download a portion or subset of the index related to a certain topic or geographical region. This allows to create a search application that makes use of this index subset and provides search features dedicated to its purpose and user expectations. Instead of dealing with a large index that makes it expensive to retrieve relevant search results, a small index makes it easier to perform accurate ranking. Furthermore, the index subset can be stored and managed on an own server, which increases the independence from external technologies. This enables 3rd party search applications without crawling Web sites and re-use partitions of the OWS index, and therefore reducing network traffic.

2.3 Personal Search

As the internet and accessible content continues to grow exponentially, the ability to quickly and accurately find relevant information has become increasingly important. However, as the volume of data on the internet increases, these search engines are starting to show their limitations. Artificial intelligence (AI) has been making significant strides in recent years, and one area where it is poised to make a considerable impact is in the realm of contextual search. Contextual search is a type of search that takes into account not only the keywords entered by the user but also the context in which those keywords are used. This means that the search engine will consider factors such as the user's location, search history, and even the time of day when determining which results to display. By taking into account above mentioned features, contextual search aims to provide users with more relevant and personalized search results².

One of the key benefits of AI-driven contextual search is its ability to provide users with personalized search results. The contextual awareness, that such engines are starting to integrate, embodies all the subtle nuances of human learning. It is the 'who', 'where', 'when', and 'why' that inform human decisions

² AI and the Future of Contextual Search: An In-depth Analysis: <https://ts2.space/en/ai-and-the-future-of-contextual-search-an-in-depth-analysis/>

and behavior³. In a real-world conversation a simple query, “How is Grandma?”, could elicit any number of potential responses depending on contextual factors, including time, circumstance, relationship, etc. Humans have an excellent communication process for conveying ideas to each other and reacting appropriately. This is due to many factors: the richness of the language they share, the common understanding of how the world works and an implicit understanding of everyday situations. In this sense, the next generation of search engines can also be regarded as recommended systems; sets of tools and techniques to provide useful recommendations and suggestions to the users to help them in the decision-making process for choosing the right products or services⁴.

With some notable exceptions, however, most Machine Learning (ML) models used for recommender systems incorporate very limited context of a specific query, relying primarily on the generic context provided by the data-set that the model is trained or fine-tuned on⁵. As a result, also most traditional recommender systems, such as those based on content-based and collaborative filtering, tend to use fairly simple user models, based on vectors of vector of item ratings⁶. In other words, the traditional systems observe mostly two types of entities, users and items, and do not put them into a context when providing recommendations^{7, 8, 9}. In applications domains, such as the recommendation in eCommerce¹⁰, personalization of content in web sites¹¹, and travel¹² and restaurant recommendation¹³, it is not sufficient to consider only information about users and items, and the context-independent representation may lead to lose predictive power since potentially useful information from multiple contexts is aggregated in a relatively static user-model. Furthermore, such approaches also raise significant concerns about bias which makes them less suited for use in many business, healthcare, and other critical applications. By taking into account factors such as a user’s search history, location, activity, company of people, intent (e.g., causal lunch, business dinner, or anniversary) and user preferences, AI can tailor the search results to better meet the user’s needs. This not only makes it easier for users to find the information they are looking for but also helps to improve the overall user experience.

³ Advancing Machine Intelligence: Why Context Is Everything: <https://towardsdatascience.com/advancing-machine-intelligence-why-context-is-everything-4bde90fb2d79>

⁴ Raza, S., & Ding, C. (2019). Progress in context-aware recommender systems—An overview. *Computer Science Review*, 31, 84-97.

⁵ Yasunaga, M., Ren, H., Bosselut, A., Liang, P., & Leskovec, J. (2021). QA-GNN: Reasoning with language models and knowledge graphs for question answering. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2104.06378*.

⁶ Kulkarni, S., & Rodd, S.F. (2020). Context Aware Recommendation Systems: A review of the state of the art techniques. *Computer Science Review*, 37

⁷ Nawara, D., & Kashef, R. (2022, April). Context-aware recommendation systems using consensus-clustering. In *2022 IEEE International Systems Conference (SysCon)* (pp. 1-8). IEEE.

⁸ Adomavicius, G., Bauman, K., Tuzhilin, A., & Unger, M. (2021). Context-Aware Recommender Systems: From Foundations to Recent Developments Context-aware recommender systems. In *Recommender Systems Handbook* (pp. 211-250). New York, NY: Springer US.

⁹ Ramirez-Garcia, X., & García-Valdez, M. (2014). Post-filtering for a restaurant context-aware recommender system. *Recent advances on hybrid approaches for designing intelligent systems*, 695-707.

¹⁰ Karimova, F. (2016). A survey of e-commerce recommender systems. *European Scientific Journal*, 12(34), 75-89.

¹¹ Martinez, L., Calles, J., & Martin, E.(2010). Ontology-based Web service to recommend spare time activities. In: *International Workshop on Information Heterogeneity and Fusion in Recommender Systems (HetRec)*, Barcelona.

¹² Chaudhari, K., & Thakkar, A. (2020). A comprehensive survey on travel recommender systems. *Archives of Computational Methods in Engineering*, 27, 1545-1571.

¹³ Al-Ghuribi, S. M., & Noah, S. A. M. (2019). Multi-criteria review-based recommender system—the state of the art. *IEEE Access*, 7, 169446-169468.

In OWS we intend to adapt and implement a contextual post-filtering approach, in which the *Location-Aware* part of the index and *Collaborative Filtering* (i.e. basic user preferences) are used to generate the first series, i.e. top-N of possibilities in the area. The concept of *Contextual Post-Filtering*, applied at the edge, is then used to adjust the ranking and further filter-out the recommendations, personalized to the user's contextual information. The goal of the application is to demonstrate how the Open Index can be exploited to create a privacy preserving user-centric application.

2.4 Conversational Search

With the rise of large language models (LLMs) for generative information retrieval (IR), a new search paradigm in the form of conversations between searchers and systems has become increasingly popular. In contrast to traditional search result pages containing ten blue links, the new paradigm rather means to show an automatically generated text summarizing (and possibly referencing) the top search results. Our concern is that this development entails the risk of advertisements being incorporated directly (in the form of brand or product placements) in the generated answers, similar to native advertising. Since advertising is a multi-billion dollar business and the main source of revenue for search engines, it seems unlikely that this opportunity to earn money will be missed in generative IR. From a user's perspective, this potential form of advertising is highly critical since it could make recognizing advertisements way more challenging than before. To raise awareness for this issue, we have conducted a preliminary study (submitted to OSSYM 2023¹⁴) in which we explore the capability of current LLMs to blend advertisements with generated search result summaries. In one scenario, we prompted GPT4 and YouChat with text snippets on a given topic and asked them to integrate subtle mentions or advertisements for a specific brand unrelated to the topic. In a second scenario, we let the models choose suitable brands to be promoted in texts about more general topics. An analysis of human assessments of the resulting responses shows that ads are difficult to include in an unrelated context and that more convincing ads can be created for brands closer to a given topic. We plan to further extend our analyses and aim at developing approaches to identify this potential form of advertising as well as approaches to counteract it, like a new kind of ad blocker for native advertising. The goal is to provide tools for more trustworthy and transparent environments in conversational search.

3. Transparency and trust concept

This section elaborates on the concepts of trust and transparency in the context of open web search, as well as their relation to each others. First, theoretical and psychological considerations based on a literature study is presented. Second, a model is presented that intends to increase informed trust based on web search transparency. This model is basis for user studies, that investigate details on trust and transparency.

3.1 Theoretical background

Despite the broad literature background in the area of trust, this multi-faceted concept expands in meaning and definitions, especially since the increased usage of search engines, artificial intelligence (AI) and digital tools in general. Therefore, the concept of trust results in more complex meanings and even more definitions, often depending on the discipline defining the concept (e.g. psychology, economics, sociology and ethics) and on the object that needs to be trusted (e.g. search engines, search

¹⁴ <https://opensearchfoundation.org/ossym2023>

results, platforms, organizations etc.). For this work, trust in search engines and search results with a focus on search applications is relevant with the goal to increase trust of the user in the general use of the OWI and emerging applications.

Several studies show that users actually have a lot of trust in search engines^{15, 16, 17} and their appraisal of search engines are more often positive than negative¹⁸. Furthermore, people trust their search engine to list the most relevant results for what they are looking for and they rely on these information. While the trust in search engines in general seems to be high, knowledge about the functionality of search engines and business models is rather low. There is also a correlation between actual knowledge and trust. People who are able to identify mechanisms like paid search marketing and search engine organisation tend to have lower levels of trust. However, there often is a big difference between actual knowledge and perceived knowledge, as people tend to overestimate themselves^{19, 20} and people with less actual knowledge are less able to accurately estimate their own knowledge, which is a common and well-known effect in psychology called the Dunning-Kruger-effect²¹. In align with this, search users are overall very confident in their perceived search abilities. This means that people might often not be aware of their lack of knowledge and, in general, they tend to overestimate their capabilities, which, in the searching process, can lead to uninformed decision-making.

The investigation of underlying reasons why people have so much trust in search engines is under-represented in current research. As mentioned above, when people tend to overestimate their own search-abilities (and they do even more when they have little actual knowledge), there might be little concerns about whether to trust search engines or not. Furthermore, people use trust mechanisms in the process of decision-making. In uncertain situations people tend to reduce the complexity of the decision making, which can be achieved by trusting.

Nevertheless, there are a number of reasons why unquestioned and uninformed trust in search engines might not be justified. For example, search results can be manipulated, user data can be reused for commercial purposes, or social biases can have influence on the search result. More elaboration on these problems are described in D6.1.

The concept of transparency is often linked to trust, because it is often suggested that a lack of transparency leads to biases on the technological side like biased selection criteria of search

¹⁵ Pan, B., Hembrooke, H., Joachims, T., Lorigo, L., Gay, G., & Granka, L. (2007). In google we trust: Users' decisions on rank, position, and relevance. *Journal of Computer-Mediated Communication*, 12(3), 801–823. doi:10.1111/j.1083-6101.2007.00351.x

¹⁶ Purcell, K., Brenner, J., & Rainie, L. (2012). Search engine use 2012. Washington, DC. https://www.eff.org/files/pew_2012_0.pdf (accessed 03 August 2023).

¹⁷ Schultheiß, S., Sünkler, S., & Lewandowski, D. (2018). We still trust in Google, but less than 10 years ago: an eye-tracking study. *Information Research*, 23(3), paper 799.

¹⁸ Schultheiß, S., & Lewandowski, D. (2023). Misplaced trust? The relationship between trust, ability to identify commercially influenced results and search engine preference. *Journal of Information Science*, 49(3), 609–623. <https://doi.org/10.1177/01655515211014157>

¹⁹ Alicke, M. D., & Govorun, O. (2005). The better-than-average effect. In *The self in social judgment* (pp. 86–106).

²⁰ Guenther, C. L., & Alicke, M. D. (2010). Deconstructing the Better-Than-Average Effect. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 99(5), 755–770. <https://doi.org/10.1037/a0020959> .

²¹ Kruger, J., & Dunning, D. (1999). Unskilled and unaware of it: How difficulties in recognizing one's own incompetence lead to inflated self-assessments. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 77(6), 1121–1134. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0022-3514.77.6.1121>

results^{22,23,24}. Therefore, there are suggestions that higher transparency would minimize these problems and lead to higher trust. However, the relation between trust and transparency is not clarified through literature. Shin and Park²⁵, for example, argue that trust itself has a moderating effect on transparency (and other related concepts like satisfaction and accountability). To our knowledge, current literature is lacking a theoretical framework, that describes the relation between trust and transparency.

A definition of the transparency concept is needed for both a theoretical framework on trust and transparency, as well as for deriving practical implications in search engines. Shin and Park (2019) consider transparency consisting of three components, namely understandability, explainability, and observability. These components can be considered in the design of a user interface that supports transparency.

The future work and next steps include both theoretical and empirical work on the trust and transparency concepts related to search engines. Since there is a lack of knowledge on the relation between trust and transparency in literature, user studies will be conducted that will investigate transparency factors that lead to increased trust. The next section outlines an initial transparency concept that will be investigated related to trust. This concept will be used as basis for the planned empirical studies.

3.2 Transparency model

This subsection outlines an initial transparency model that describes what information can be made transparent. This model serves as a basis for user studies, where its actual impact on trust will be researched. Each of the three aspects listed below includes a research question that should be answered in the respective studies. The purpose of this model is to inform about the design of search front-ends and search applications to increase trust. Furthermore, it also outlines requirements on the index which information would be required for this purpose.

The model takes into account the aforementioned concepts understandability, explainability, and observability, and adds controllability. Thus, it suggests to disclose information of the search process in an understandable way and to enable users take over control of this information. From this three transparency areas can be derived.

As described above, people tend to trust better, if they lack knowledge of potential problems, downsides, or risks. In this model trust is regarded as informed trust. So it is important to mention that this model and the upcoming empirical studies address trust, based on knowledge about potential problems of web search. Hence, in order to investigate the relation between transparency and trust in user studies, the users need to be informed about potential ethical problems of web search.

a) Information on web documents

During the indexing process several types of information related to web documents are available for collection or can be created through analysis. First, web documents have contextual information, such as location, country, server, or creation data. Second, web documents have metadata inside the

²² Epstein, R., & Robertson, R. E. (2015). The search engine manipulation effect (SEME) and its possible impact on the outcomes of elections. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 112(33), E4512-E4521. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1419828112>

²³ Pariser, E. (2011). *The Filter Bubble: What the internet is hiding from you*. Penguin Books.

²⁴ van Hoboken, J. (2012). *Search engine freedom: On the implications of the right to freedom of expression for the legal governance of web search engines*. https://pure.uva.nl/ws/files/1769429/104098_thesis.pdf

²⁵ Shin, D., & Park, Y. J. (2019). Role of fairness, accountability, and transparency in algorithmic affordance. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 98, 277–284. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chb.2019.04.019>

document, such as title, author, publisher. Third, the documents have file information when locally stored, such as file size or document type. Fourth, basic classifications from document analysis can be derived, such as the language. Fifth, a wide range of qualitative information can be analysed, such as the nutrition labels²⁶.

This information makes the search process observable. However, it also results in a magnitude of information of different types and levels. Hence, the question arises which information should be shown to the user and how would the respective information type contribute to the trust of the user. In particular, it will be researched which information users are willing to take up and which cognitive load is acceptable.

b) Information on the search process and open web search

A different type of information is related to the search process as such and the concept of open web search. General information can be provided to the user in an understandable way how the search and retrieval process works and how the models are processed, indexed, and ranked. Furthermore, the concept of open web search can also be explained in this context. The explained concepts also depend on the respective search application, as they might process data from the index differently.

This information makes the search process and result presentation explainable. It leads to the question on which level of detail the user is interested in such information and how it contributes to trust.

c) Controlling the search process

Instead of providing information, the user can also be enabled to actively influence the search process and the result presentation. For example, based on the metadata described above (information about the web documents), the user can add filters to the search results. Other examples of controlling the search process are the influence on the presentation of the search result, the ranking algorithm, or selection of the index source.

This method makes the search process controllable. The question arises, if this has an impact on trust. Though an influence on the user experience (e.g. satisfaction) is likely, it is not clear if and how it influences trust. So a study will address the relation between an user interface that enables the user to control the retrieval process and which influence this has on trust.

4. Privacy concept

In an age where the Internet is simply an indispensable part of life, the use of a search engine is possibly at the foundation of the user experience. The instantaneous access to information is not simply a 'nice to have' for researchers. It became the bedrock of our modern consumer society. At the same time privacy became a significant issue in this age of information (see also deliverable D6.1). Activities that were once private or shared with the few now leave trails of data that expose our interests, traits, beliefs, and intentions. We communicate using e-mails, texts, and social media; find partners on dating sites; learn via online courses; seek responses to mundane and sensitive questions using search engines; read news and books in the cloud; navigate streets with geotracking systems; and celebrate our newborns, and mourn our dead, on social media profiles. Through these and other activities, we reveal information - both knowingly and unwittingly - to one another, to commercial entities, and to our governments. It is not only Google, all players in the search engine space, such as Microsoft's Bing, Yahoo Search and Baidu, are mining consumer data. Of course search engines offer an essential

²⁶ Fuhr, N., Nejd, W., Peters, I., Stein, B., Giachanou, A., Grefenstette, G., Gurevych, I. et al. (2018). An Information Nutritional Label for Online Documents. ACM SIGIR Forum. 51(3), pp. 46-66. doi:10.1145/3190580.3190588.

service, however, that service is certainly not free of cost. The cost is a certain level of intrusion into our lives in the form of search engine companies like Google gathering data about our online habits and using that data to fine tune marketing efforts (often by selling that data to third parties for their use), but also benefits from inferring user habits and interests.

The main issue evolves around awareness and permission. Namely, “Are search engine companies free to gather and use our data without explicit permission - can we opt out of such an arrangement?”. The cornerstones of OWS end-user application will be a privacy framework built around trust, awareness and permission.

4.1 Privacy-preserving mechanisms

Privacy commonly relates to the meaning that sensitive information about individuals or groups is not disclosed to others. Although privacy and confidentiality are overlapped in some contexts, they appear somewhat different, in terms of their concepts and protection methods²⁷. Loss of confidentiality is mostly caused by the weakness of access control or encryption schemes, while loss of privacy is associated with not only that but also the vulnerabilities in the control of data utilization and data analytics (leading to linking attacks, inference attacks, etc.). Privacy-preserving protection methods take into account the utility of data besides the protection of privacy. Confidentiality is realized primarily by encryption and access control. Cryptography is also utilized to preserve privacy in terms of keeping the data confidential. Besides cryptographic tools, privacy is also preserved by perturbation (to mask the true data value) and anonymization (to hide the 'data-data owner' links) techniques. Blockchain and Distributed Ledger Technology can further contribute to create a secure distributed ecosystem in which data can be used with the required permission.

4.1.1 Cryptography and Homomorphic Encryption

Cryptographic methods mostly employ Secure Multi-party Computation²⁸, delivered by some form of Homomorphic Encryption schemes^{29,30}. These methods preserve privacy by keeping private data items in encrypted forms, then performing utility functionalities on encrypted individual data items to get encrypted aggregate results, and finally decrypting these results to get the outputs of the same functionalities as if on plain individual data items.

An example would be preservation of the user location using Homomorphic Encryption. The user encrypts data with the public key before transferring it to the cloud. The cloud server can perform calculations and computations on the cipher text, but it cannot decrypt the results of the computations as it does not have the private key. The server responds the cipher text back to the user who can decrypt the results to get the desired results. Under a similar fashion one can encrypt any text-based query data³¹. For trustworthy services, i.e. services where user's consent for their personalized data to be

²⁷ Tran, H. Y., & Hu, J. (2019). Privacy-preserving big data analytics a comprehensive survey. *Journal of Parallel and Distributed Computing*, 134, 207-218.

²⁸ Goldreich, O. (1998). Secure multi-party computation. Manuscript. Preliminary version, 78(110).

²⁹ Pulido-Gaytan, B., Tchernykh, A., Cortés-Mendoza, J. M., Babenko, M., Radchenko, G., Avetisyan, A., & Drozdov, A. Y. (2021). Privacy-preserving neural networks with homomorphic encryption: C challenges and opportunities. *Peer-to-Peer Networking and Applications*, 14(3), 1666-1691.

³⁰ Khedr, A., Gulak, G., & Vaikuntanathan, V. (2015). SHIELD: scalable homomorphic implementation of encrypted data-classifiers. *IEEE Transactions on Computers*, 65(9), 2848-2858.

³¹ Wu, Q, He, K., & Chen X. (2020). Personalized Federated Learning for Intelligent IoT Applications: A Cloud-Edge Based Framework. *IEEE Open Journal of the Computer Society*, 1, pp. 35–44. Doi: 10.1109/OJCS.2020.2993259

used, asymmetric cryptography can be exploited. Asymmetric cryptography uses a pair of keys for encryption and decryption. A public key is used for encryption and a private key is used for decryption. The messages encoded using public keys can only be decoded by trusted end-points which were assigned private keys.

Although cryptographic computation can guarantee “perfect” privacy in terms of keeping data confidential by the security strength of cryptographic primitives, the weaknesses are challenges in the scalability and implementation efficiency, which is mostly due to the high computational complexity of existing homomorphic encryption schemes.

A non-perturbative method preserves privacy by sanitizing identifiable information, thereby preventing identity from being connected with an adversary’s background information.

4.1.2 Obfuscation and perturbation

Obfuscation and data perturbation techniques use similar approaches. Among the perturbation approaches, Polat et al.³² proposed hiding personal data statistically while generating recommendations, which were later, proved insecure³³. Shokri et al.³⁴ proposed a distributed obfuscation-based CF technique by allowing local user profile modifications while hiding the real profile from an untrusted central server. However, this approach requires trading-off between privacy and recommendation accuracy³⁵.

4.1.2 Differential privacy

The main idea behind the differential privacy is that a differentially private recommended result is not sensitive to any single user. Thus, it is a perfect notion to prevent the inference attack (e.g. on a recommender system). If a user’s once purchase of an item does not cause an obvious change of a recommended list to that item, an attacker could not guess the purchased item with a high confidence just by observing the change of the output. In most systems differential privacy is achieved by adding noise to hide user data. For instance, McSherry et al.³⁶ address the privacy issue in recommender systems using Laplace noise. They add Laplace noise to the movie average rating, user average rating and covariance matrix. Then the noisy matrices are released and used in the current recommender algorithm. Moritz Hardt et al.³⁷ convert the recommendation problem into the Matrix Completion problem, which tries to recover the missing entries of a matrix under a partially given matrix with a subset of the entries are randomly sampled.

³² Polat, H, & Du, W. (2005). SVD-based collaborative filtering with privacy. In: Proceedings of the 2005 ACM Symposium on Applied Computing, pp. 791–795. doi: 10.1145/1066677.1066860

³³ Zhang, S., Ford, J., & Makedon, F. (2006). Deriving Private Information from Randomly Perturbed Ratings. In: Proceedings of the 2006 SIAM International Conference on Data Mining (SDM), pp. 59-69. doi:10.1137/1.9781611972764.6.

³⁴ Shokri, R., Pedarsani, P. & Theodorakopoulos, G., & Hubaux, J.-P. (2009). Preserving privacy in collaborative filtering through distributed aggregation of offline profiles. In Proceedings of the third ACM conference on Recommender systems. ACM, pp. 157–164.

³⁵ Badsha, S., Yi, X., Khalil, I., & Bertino, E. (2017, June). Privacy preserving user-based recommender system. In 2017 IEEE 37th international conference on Distributed Computing Systems (ICDCS) (pp. 1074-1083). IEEE.

³⁶ McSherry F, Mironov I. (2009). Differentially private recommender systems: Building privacy into the Netflix Prize contenders. In Proceedings of the 15th ACM SIGKDD international conference on Knowledge discovery and data mining (KDD '09), pp. 627-636. ACM:New York, NY, USA. <https://doi.org/10.1145/1557019.1557090>

³⁷ Hardt, M. & Roth, A. (2012). Beating randomized response on incoherent matrices. In Proceedings of the forty-fourth annual ACM symposium on Theory of computing (STOC '12). Association for Computing Machinery, pp. 1255–1268. New York, NY, USA. <https://doi.org/10.1145/2213977.2214088>

4.2 Prototype of Privacy preserving Personalized Search

As outlined in *Section 2.3*, we treat Personalized Search as a contextually aware recommendation system. Since recommenders operate by processing, collecting and analyzing numerous user data, serious privacy concerns are raised. To at least partially mitigate these concerns the idea in OWS is to a) separate the contextual awareness aspect of the search from its user matching aspect and b) implement the recommender, using distributed recommender and a homomorphic encryption scheme. The concept is outlined in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Architectural overview of the privacy-preserving, personalized and location-aware search engine implemented as a context aware recommender.

The overall concept, outlined in Figure 1, was designed to protect the privacy of the users. Namely, personalized search/recommendation typically makes selections based on user's past preferences and preferences of the similar users. Thus, the more information each user provides about personal preferences, the more meaningful the recommendations will be. However, at the same time, the more information is revealed to the server on the user-item relations, the lower the users' privacy is. This also means that in traditional systems potential of privacy breach is significant. As outlined in Figure 1, we conceptualize a distributed mechanism for users to augment their profiles in a way that obfuscates the user-item connection to an untrusted server. In principle, each user has two version of its profiles, an online (on and untrusted server), stored as an aggregated model and the offline (located on the user's side), stored as a local model. The offline model is basically a set of user preferences, which consists an up to date information on their item preferences (i.e. item profile), personal preferences and activity

(i.e. user-profile) and current context. The online profile is frequently synchronized with the offline version using methods, such as, federated/distributed (multi-view) matrix factorization. The online profiles are then used to get top N results using collaborative filtering and the offline profile is used on the device directly for further personalization of recommendations using post filtering (*Please see section 5.3 Location-based application for more details on the implementation*).

5. Search Application Designs

This section provides initial concepts of vertical search applications. Beside the two search applications dedicated to the tasks T4.1 and T4.2, there is also a search application included that stems from an external use case of two startup companies. The section starts with the description of a prototype application that demonstrates the underlying technical concept and serves as basis and blueprint for the other search applications. Though the development of these applications officially starts in M13, a need for the initial design has been identified, in order to align them with the OWS infrastructure.

5.1 Prototype application

The prototype application is a first trial how to develop a search application based on the OWS infrastructure and based on an index partition. Its first goal is to try out the overall concept of a search application by including the key components in the development. The second goal is to provide a blueprint or guiding example for other search application developers.

Conceptual Design

The overall concept of a vertical search engine consists of two parts, the OWI and the search application (see Figure 2). The term search application is used for the stand-alone search component with imported index partition.

Figure 2: Conceptual architecture of the prototype search application

The OWI contains a vast corpus' of data collected from the World Wide Web and maintains it in data centres distributed throughout Europe. It allows to download partitions of the index that can be incorporated by a search application. An index partition is structured as Common Index File Format (CIFF)³⁸ and Apache Parquet³⁹.

CIFF aims to enable sharing and utilization of inverted indexes across different search systems. It provides a standardized format for representing index data, allowing multiple search engines to access and utilize the same index files. This format originates in academia for searching indexes from various information retrieval systems and comparing their performance. However, in an industrial setting, it cannot directly be used by most search libraries due to their own internal index formats. Therefore, in order to utilize the CIFF index, third party developers must convert it to the internal index format of the search library that they use. To resolve this issue, CIFF-Lucene converter⁴⁰ can be used to generate an index that can be used by Apache Lucene. Lucene has been chosen, since it is used as search engine library by commonly used search engine systems, such as Elasticsearch and Apache Solr.

In addition to index data, the Open Web Index also provides metadata of webpages in Parquet format. When creating the OpenWebSearch.eu index, the original content of the websites goes through common pre-processing steps like stop-word removal, stemming, lemmatization, lower casing and so on. However, snippets of original website data in conjunction with their links make for richer results in search applications. In order to preserve this original data, full text without format style information is stored in the metadata. Furthermore, the original metadata of the web pages and data stemming from the page analysis data are stored. These metadata are exported along with the index data in the Parquet format, which is a columnar storage file format widely used in big data processing and analytics frameworks such as Apache Hadoop and Apache Spark. It is designed to optimize I/O performance for large-scale data processing. The columnar data storage has several benefits including columnar compression, schema evolution without dataset rewrites and efficient queries by reading columns.

The core of the search service is the search application that coordinates the search and retrieval process. It provides a REST API that accepts search queries and returns search results. In order to perform the actual search, it makes use of Lucene that accesses the partitioned index converted to the native Lucene format. Using the metadata information, the preliminary search result can be limited and ranked, as well as enriched with full text snippets. The web application provides the user interface where search queries are created and results are displayed. This can be done in classic style with text field and link list, but also other forms are possible.

Prototype Search Application

Based on the conceptual design of the OpenWebSearch.eu project, we created a prototype (blueprint or guiding example) search application⁴¹ that can be used by future search applications. This application includes a REST API that is intended for direct use by developers who wish to create search applications using the Open Web Index. The application requires developers to place their CIFF index along with its corresponding Parquet file into the indexes folder. It converts the CIFF index into an Apache Lucene index folder which forms the basis of the Search REST API. The API searches primarily over this Lucene index. The compressed Parquet file corresponding to the index is converted internally to a CSV file,

³⁸ J. Lin et al. (2020). Supporting interoperability between open-source search engines with the common index file format. arXiv preprint arXiv. doi:10.48550/arXiv.2003.08276

³⁹ <https://parquet.apache.org/>

⁴⁰ <https://github.com/informagi/lucene-ciff>

⁴¹ <https://github.com/rkaushik29/java-lucene-search-api>

using the Python library “parquet-tools”⁴². The CSV file is queried by the application through column pruning, allowing for efficient large scale data retrieval. This allows rich metadata to be returned by the REST API along with the index search results. The REST API is written in Java, and built using Apache Maven. The developer simply needs to run:

```
start_app.sh $index-name
```

This will first convert the CIFF index to a Lucene index and start the REST API at localhost:8000, and enable Cross Origin Resource Sharing (CORS) from localhost:3000 by default. This allows any front-end application hosted on the latter to access and send requests to the API, independent of the API itself. The CORS and hosting ports can be changed from these defaults as required.

The application also allows developers to retrieve an Apache Lucene index from the CIFF index by running a separate “convert_index” script. This allows developers to use this index with other search libraries of their choice, like ElasticSearch, Solr and Cassandra.

Demonstration

The Prototype Search Application⁴³ can be used to make any search application on the internet. To demonstrate this, we created a search application for popular sightseeing locations in Graz, Austria. The second demonstration is an application that allows to specify the search domain.

a) Sightseeing Search

To create this application, a CIFF index file that indexed data of popular attractions in Graz was generated by the Open Web Search project. Using our index converter, the CIFF index was converted to an Apache Lucene index. The Parquet file containing URL metadata was also procured. These resources are sufficient and necessary to start the prototype application. Following this, the prototype application can be started and hosted on a server.

Simultaneously, a basic front-end application was created and hosted on a server using React.js which sends search queries as GET requests to the API. The API returns search results as URLs and metadata which are then displayed on the front-end. A visualization of the results is shown in Figure 3.

⁴² <https://github.com/ktrueda/parquet-tools>

⁴³ The application will be published end of 2023

Figure 3: User interface of the front-end of the sightseeing application

b) Personalised Search

The nature of the prototype search application allows for the creation of personalised search applications. If the application is given multiple ClFF index files along with their corresponding Parquet files, the user has the ability to choose the index they want to perform the search in. This allows multiple indexes to be searched by a single API, depending on user preference.

5.2 Science Search application

The goal of this application is to enable the search for different types of geo-science information, including scientific publications, satellite images, research data, and news information. A web search should deliver all types of information in a combined search result view. Target group of this application are people interested in geo-science research, including researchers in this field.

A potential use case is the search for dryness in a particular region. A user can search in a search field for "dryness Tuscany" which will result in a list of research papers, research projects, and news pages on this topic. Then the region will be translated to geo-coordinates and a second search can be done on an Earth Observation Asset Catalogue (EOAC). An EOAC is a database that contains various information outlined on geographical maps. It allows to search this database using location and time as search parameters. By using the search term "dryness" and translating the region "Tuscany" to geo-coordinates, the EOAC can be searched automatically and will result geographical maps where dryness is illustrated. The same procedure can be performed vice versa. A geographic search (graphical search on a map) in the EOAC with a specific topic will first result geographical maps and will then be translated to a search term so that the geo-science index can be searched, which results in scientific papers and news pages related to the geographic search. This use case is outlined in Figure 4.

Figure 4: Information flow of the science search use case.

The overall software architecture to enable the use case is illustrated in Figure 5. The information sources are shown on the left side. First, websites containing news on geo-science are taken into account, such as websites of research institutes. Second, scientific databases are used that include scientific information, such as project descriptions on GitLab or descriptions of research data on Zenodo. Third, OpenAleks is used to retrieve scientific papers on geo-science. Fourth, Earth Observation Asset Catalogues are used that allow to retrieve geographical maps that contain topical information, such as dryness in a particular region.

The first and second sources are web based and can be indexed by the OWS infrastructure. During the indexing process the pages are analysed regarding their geographical locations and respective metadata with geo-coordinates are generated and assigned to the pages. Then an index partition is downloaded that is restricted to geo-science pages. The index partition consists of a CIFF and PARQUET file that are imported in the local application search engine (see also Section 5.1). The other two information sources are queried directly, as they do not contain data in web-based format that can be indexed.

The central component of this vertical search engine is the application service. This service coordinates the search process by integrating user search requests with the different types of search tasks. To this end, a knowledge graph is used that provides semantic information needed to relate the different types of search queries, such as the translation of a region to coordinates. The user interface accepts different types of queries (search terms and geographical search) and presents the integrated results. It will also allow to to a step-by-step search (faceted search) that allows to start with one search type and provides the user with other search possibilities based on the result of the previous search.

Figure 5: Conceptual architecture of the science search application.

In order to enable this search application, several requirements are posed on the OWS infrastructure, including (a) indexing geoscience search pages and databases, (b) tagging pages with geo-locations, and (c) creation of index partitions based on the topic of geo-science. In a first step a pre-defined list of URLs will be used to define the corpus of geo-science web pages.

5.3 Location-based application

The aim of this application is to showcase how Open Index can be used to create more personalized (user-centered) and privacy preserving searches; with a rating system that is not impacted by ads and capital investments and can integrate user's context in a privacy preserving way.

The application will support users to find restaurants in Ljubljana and Maribor. The search takes into account current location, personal food and restaurant preferences (e.g. cuisine), and restaurant information (opening hours) and the user's contextual information (e.g. day of the week, time of the day, location, activity, company of people, intent, user's search history, user's past ratings and sentiment, etc.) in order to display a personalized list of matching restaurants (recommendations) as a list or on a map (using open maps, such as Open Maps for Europe, HERE WeGo, etc.). The overall architecture is outlined in Figure 6.

Figure 6: The conceptual architecture of the location-based search application.

As outlined in Figure 6 the OWS Crawler will index the data from existing restaurant platforms such as TripAdvisor, Yelp, Zomato, Open table etc. Initially we foresee the Open Index to maintain information such as, descriptions of the restaurants, images, user ratings and comments, information on type of eating (e.g., dinner, breakfast, lunch), cultural/ethnic classification, (Chinese, Italian, French, Contemporary, Modern, Classic, etc.), type of food (pasta, sea-food, home made, vegetarian, vegan, gluten free, etc.) and appropriateness for occasion (e.g. family friendly, pet friendly, business, casual, etc.). A subset of the index would be downloaded and maintained locally at the edge (e.g. in the local infrastructure of the region/city). When users access the search engine a Top-N recommendations are generated based on the location and similarity with other users. That is, a collaborative filtering algorithm^{44,45} is used to select the most N relevant choices. The model makes a prediction based on preferences of similar users/customers by modelling the user-item connection to make possible recommendations. It will be based on user-user approaches and the idea that similar users exhibit similar preferences. The item-item approach then recommends items to a user based on the similar type of items rated by the same user in the past. In this sense, in OWS we target the user-item approaches that will have the ability to recommend serendipitous items which may not have been a part of the user's history, but still match the general preferential profile of the user. In order to enable the first-stage of the search/recommendation a generic user-preference model is created and maintained. User browsing history is of particular interest because it serves⁴⁶ as a reliable source for extracting user-preferences and is also domain independent. However, this raises significant privacy issues. We

⁴⁴ Tripathi, A., & Sharma, A. K. (2020, June). Recommending restaurants: A collaborative filtering approach. In 2020 8th International Conference on Reliability, Infocom Technologies and Optimization (Trends and Future Directions)(ICRITO) (pp. 1165-1169). IEEE.

⁴⁵ Al-Ghobari, M., Muneer, A., & Fati, S. M. (2021). Location-Aware Personalized Traveler Recommender System (LAPTA) Using Collaborative Filtering KNN. Computers, Materials & Continua, 69(2).

⁴⁶ Rajendran, D. P. D., & Sundarraj, R. P. (2021). Using topic models with browsing history in hybrid collaborative filtering recommender system: Experiments with user ratings. International Journal of Information Management Data Insights, 1(2), 100027.

will adopt secure multi-party computation⁴⁷ in order to calculate the user-item similarity and apply post-filtering locally, on the user's phone, in order to obtain recommendations with privacy. This will ensure that sensitive information such as name, address, age, gender, and financial information, never leave the user's device as well as prevent user's interests and activities, to be used for potential profiling outside the context of the recommendations.

The contextual post-filtering approach exploits the user's contextual information to adjust and re-order the top-N recommendations by: (1) filtering out recommendations that are irrelevant, and (2) adjusting the ranking of recommendations on the list. Figure 7 visualizes the approach.

Figure 7: The outline of the privacy preserving post filtering

As outlined in Figure 7 the proposed recommender system will implement collaborative filtering to find restaurants for the user. The similarity between the active user and top-N users is used to obtain a weighted average of ratings for each particular item. The similarity is to be implemented using Pearson's correlation. The output of the collaborative filtering algorithm, i.e. the top-N items, are returned to the mobile application, where the list is adjusted according to the user's context. Overall, a deep model (an Auto-encoder) is deployed to evaluate the average of ratings in a given specific context. The proposed model is to be formed by connecting multiple AEs and NN. The input data will include multiple feature vectors. The input and output data for the autoencoder will include user vectors, item vectors and context vectors. A final comparison is carried out to compare (1) the average post-filtering a restaurant has in the current context (that is the mean of user ratings) and (2) the rating predicted by the collaborative filtering algorithm.

The contextual information will be obtained in different ways:

⁴⁷ Li, D., Chen, C., Lv, Q., Shang, L., Zhao, Y., Lu, T., & Gu, N. (2016). An algorithm for efficient privacy-preserving item-based collaborative filtering. *Future Generation Computer Systems*, 55, 311-320.

- Explicitly - by directly approaching the user with direct questions and by registering their feedback related to the restaurant and the recommendation engine in the application.
- Implicitly - from the data or the environment, such as a change in location of the user detected by a smartphone application or GPS. Alternatively, temporal contextual information can be implicitly obtained from the timestamp of a transaction. The source of the implicit contextual information will be accessed directly from the user's phone and the data extracted from it, used on the phone directly (not shared).

5.4 Repair support application

In addition to the science search and location-based search applications, an external use case has been discussed. This use case is based on a joint project of the two Austrian startup companies Xatooza⁴⁸ and ar:met⁴⁹. Their joint project (business model) aims to help people to repair their own devices (e.g. coffee machine or washing machine) using augmented reality (AR) technologies. The idea is that users can get help through an AR app from an expert depending on the type of the broken device. They develop the AR technology so that an expert can give advice over internet how to fix the device. Due to the various types of devices, the companies manage a database of different experts, which in fact is a selected list of expert and company websites.

In order to enable a match making between client and expert, they need a web search functionality in their system. The key requirement consists in a restriction of the search on the set of expert websites. This use case is outlined in Figure 8.

⁴⁸ <https://www.xatooza.com/>

⁴⁹ <https://www.armet.at/>

Figure 8: Use case of the repair support application

This case perfectly fits to our project's concept of providing an index partition for an own search engine. While Google does not allow such a restriction for a greater number of websites and also does not allow a change of their ranking, an OWS-based application can be better tailored to these needs. In order to create a client-expert match making search application, they can follow the concept outlined in Section 5.1. First, they have to download an index partition based on the list of expert websites. Then they convert it to the Lucene index format, and build a search application based on Lucene. Micro formats will be used in the company or expert websites that can be extracted by OWS and included in the index and metadata.

The actual development of this application is subject to the two startup companies. However, the discussion of this use case was valuable to define the overall search concept and defines requirements for the development of the OWI infrastructure.

6. Conclusion and Outlook

This deliverable presents an initial set of support methods how to develop search applications using the OWS infrastructure. It consists of both technical advices how to create a search application, as well as models for ensuring transparency, trust and privacy. Thus it provides the grounding for the development of the first search applications.

The upcoming work will include the development of the first versions of the science search application (Task 4.1) and the location-based search application (Task 4.2). Furthermore, empirical studies will be conducted on how to increase trust, based on transparency (Task 4.5) and privacy (Task 4.4). The further development of the privacy model (Task 4.4) will be conducted along with the location-based search application. The development of the conversational search application (Task 4.3) and the user-centered evaluation of the search applications will be conducted later, mainly in the third project year.

Appendix

See included the list of Acronyms and Abbreviations used in OWS context.

Acronym / Abbreviation	Term
AR	Augmented Reality
ML	Machine Learning
OSSYM	Open Search Symposium
OWI	Open Web Index
OWS or OWS.eu	OpenWebSearch.eu project